

Ionic liquid as base and phase transfer agent : A green protocol for the synthesis of diaryl sulphides in water[†]

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Manuscript received 09 July 2013, accepted 11 July 2013

Abstract : A basic ionic liquid, 1-methyl-3-butylimidazolium hydroxide, [BMIm]OH, acts as a base and phase transfer agent in the copper-catalysed ligand free *S*-arylation in water. A variety of iodo and bromoaryl compounds undergo coupling with aryl and heteroaryl thiols in presence of this ionic liquid in water to provide the corresponding diaryl/ aryl-heteroaryl sulfides. The use of benign [BMIm]OH and water as reaction medium makes this procedure greener and cost effective.

Keywords : Ionic liquid, CuO nanoparticles, water, C-S coupling, organo-sulfides.

Introduction

Ionic liquids are of considerable interest in the context of green synthesis because of their wide acceptability as alternative green reaction media¹. In the last two decades, ionic liquids have been employed as efficient catalysts for several organic reactions². A few years ago we have introduced a unique task specific ionic liquid, 1-methyl-3-butylimidazolium hydroxide [BMIm]OH, as an efficient catalyst and solvent in Michael addition³ and Knoevenagel condensation⁴. The remarkable efficiency of this ionic liquid in such C-C bond formation reactions encouraged us to find its importance in metal catalysed carbon-heteroatom bond-forming reactions.

Aryl C-S bond-forming reaction is an important tool in the synthesis of organo-sulfides which have useful applications as pharmaceutically active agents, organic materials and intermediates in organic synthesis⁵. A number of aryl sulphides are also used for the treatment of cancer⁶, Alzheimer disease⁷ and HIV⁸. A variety of metals including Pd⁹, Cu¹⁰, Co¹¹, Ni¹² and more recently Fe¹³ usually in presence of a ligand have been used for aryl-sulfur bond formation by the coupling of aryl halides with thiols. However, the high cost and air sensitivity of Pd catalysts and often tedious procedure for the prepara-

tion of ligands restrict their applications in large-scale processes. On the other hand, in general, Co and Ni catalysts are associated with toxicity. Moreover metal-catalysed *S*-arylations are performed in hazardous solvents like DMF, DMSO, NMP etc. In recent times, interest in nanoparticle catalysis has increased tremendously because of its high efficiency and compatibility with eco-friendly reaction medium¹⁴

Reactions in water have attracted considerable interest because of their environmental acceptability and low cost¹⁵. Moreover, water often exhibits unique reactivity and selectivity that cannot be achieved using other solvents¹⁶. So, water is our obvious choice as reaction medium. Although copper-catalysed C-S bond-forming reactions are widely explored in ligand-free conditions¹⁷ in different organic solvents, only few protocols are known to accomplish *S*-arylation in water as thiol has the inherent tendency towards dimerization. These procedures usually involve strong bases like KOH, Cs₂CO₃ and TBAB as additive¹⁸

Here we report a CuO nanoparticle catalysed ligand-free C-S bond-forming reaction in water using [BMIm]OH ionic liquid as base and phase transfer reagent (Scheme 1).

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

X = I, Br

Ar¹ and Ar² = aryl, heteroaryl**Scheme 1.** Basic ionic liquid-mediated copper-catalysed *S*-arylation in water.**Results and discussion**

To standardize the reaction conditions a series of experiments have been performed in water using different copper catalysts, phase transfer agents, base, temperature and time for a representative reaction of thiophenol and iodobenzene (Table 1).

Table 1. Standardization of reaction conditions

Entry	Catalyst	Additive	Temp. (°C)	Time (h)	Base	Yield (%) ^a
1	CuI	-	100	12	K ₃ PO ₄	trace
2	CuI	SDS	100	12	K ₃ PO ₄	29
3	CuI	TBAB	100	12	K ₃ PO ₄	65
4	CuO nps	TBAB	100	12	K ₃ PO ₄	85
5	CuO nps	TBAB	100	12	-	trace
6	CuO nps	[BMIm]OH	100	12	-	90
7	CuO nps	[BMIm]OH	rt	24	-	trace
8	Cu ₂ O nps	[BMIm]OH	100	12	-	87
9	Cu(0) nps	[BMIm]OH	100	12	-	81
10	Cu ₂ O nps	[BMIm]Br	100	24	-	trace
11	CuO nps	[BMIm]BF ₄	100	24	-	trace
12	CuO nps	[BMIm]BF ₄	100	12	Cs ₂ CO ₃	80
13	CuO nps	PEG-2000	100	24	-	trace

^aYield of isolated product.

The best yield was obtained using 5 mol% of CuO as catalyst and [BMIm]OH (2 equivalents) as base as well as phase transfer agent in water at 100 °C for 12 h (Table 1, entry 6). Homogeneous CuI is found to be less active in ligand free conditions in water (Table 1, entries 1–3). Both Cu₂O and Cu⁰ nanoparticles are also found to catalyse the reaction with comparable efficiency using [BMIm]OH (Table 1, entries 8–9). Different phase transfer additives like TBAB (Table 1, entry 5) and PEG-2000 (Table 1, entry 13) are unable to initiate the reaction without any base. It may be noted that in our reaction process the cationic part of the ionic liquid bearing an alkyl chain is

serving as a phase transfer agent whereas the negative counterpart is acting as a base. Thus the demand of a base and phase transfer agent in *S*-arylation in water medium was fulfilled by our [BMIm]OH ionic liquid. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report where a basic ionic liquid plays this type of dual character in C–S bond formation in water.

Thus, in a typical general experimental procedure, a mixture of thiophenol and aryl iodide in presence of CuO nanoparticles and [BMIm]OH was heated at 100 °C in water for a certain period of time as required to complete the reaction (TLC). Standard work-up and purification by column chromatography provided the pure product.

The reaction was studied with a wide range of aryl/heteroaryl halides and thiols. The results are summarized in Table 2. Various electron-donating groups such as -Me, -OMe, -dimethyl and electron withdrawing groups like -COMe, -CN, -NO₂ in *ortho*, *meta* and *para* positions are compatible under the reaction conditions. When the reaction was performed with bromo-iodobenzene, *S*-

Table 2. Representative examples of *S*-arylations in water using CuO NP and [BMIm]OH

Entry	Thiol	Haloaryl	Product	Yield (%) ^a	Time (h)
1				90	12
2				81	12
3				86	12
4				83	14
5				81	12
6				85	12
7				82	12
8				83	14
9				80	12
10				78	12
11				88	12

^aYield of isolated product.

arylation occurs selectively with -iodo group, keeping -Br moiety intact in the aromatic ring (Table 2, entries 6–7). No intermolecular coupling was observed when reaction was performed with 4-bromothiophenol (Table 2, entries 3 and 6). The reaction between a heteroaryl thiol (2-mercaptopyridine) and heteroaryl (thiophene) bromide was accomplished successfully by this procedure (Table 2, entry 11). These diheteroaryl sulphides having significant biological activities are of much interest¹⁹.

In general, all the reactions are clean and high yielding. The products are obtained with high purity after simple column chromatography. Both CuO nanoparticles and the ionic liquid were recovered after the reaction and was recycled upto five times with gradual marginal loss of activity.

In a typical reaction pathway, CuO nanoparticles undergo oxidative addition with aryl halide in the first step, leading to the formation of the intermediate **A**. Then S–H bond of thiol is activated by basic part of ionic liquid [BMIm]OH and the thiol moiety is transferred to the metal centre with expulsion of halide ion from **A**. This leads to the formation of another intermediate **B**. The final product is obtained via the reductive elimination from **B** and the regenerated catalyst takes part in the next cycle (Scheme 1)²⁰.

Scheme 2. Probable mechanism.

Experimental

[BMIm]OH was prepared following our earlier procedure⁴. After the preparation of basic ionic liquid, it was passed through a basic alumina packed column to make it free from KOH. This ionic liquid is considerably stable under ambient conditions and can be used in reactions without any difficulty.

IR spectra were taken as thin films for liquid compounds and as KBr pellets for solids. NMR spectra were recorded at 300 and 500 MHz for ¹H NMR and at 75 and 125 MHz for ¹³C NMR in CDCl₃ solutions.

Representative procedure for the coupling of thiophenol with iodobenzene (Table 2, entry 1) : To a solution of iodobenzene (204 mg, 1 mmol) and thiophenol (121 mg, 1.0 mmol) in water (5 mL) was added [BMIm]OH (300 mg, 2 mmol) and CuO nanoparticle catalyst (4 mg, 5 mol%) and the mixture was heated at 100 °C (oil bath) for a period of time required for completion (TLC). The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and extracted with Et₂O (30 mL). The ether extract was washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated to leave the crude product which was purified by column chromatography over silica gel (hexane) to provide pure diphenyl sulfide as a colourless oil; yield : 168 mg (90%). The spectroscopic data (¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR) of this product are in good agreement with those of an authentic sample^{21b}.

This procedure was followed for all the reactions listed in Table 2. Most of these products are known compounds and they are identified by comparison of their spectroscopic data (¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR) with those reported. The unknown compound (Table 2, entry 11) is properly characterized by its spectroscopic (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and HR-MS) data. The characterisation data of all products are provided below in order of their entries in Table 2.

Diphenyl sulphide (Table 2, entry 1)^{21b} : Colourless liquid; IR (neat) : 3038, 2884, 1476 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.23–7.25 (1H, m), 7.30–7.36 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 127.2, 129.3 (2C), 131.2 (2C), 135.9.

(4-Methoxyphenyl)(4-nitrophenyl)sulfane (Table 2, entry 2)^{21a} : Yellow viscous oil; IR (neat) : 2887, 1446, 1395 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.86 (3H, s), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.08 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.48 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 8.03 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 55.6, 115.8 (2C), 120.3, 124.1 (2C), 125.7 (2C), 137.3 (2C), 145.2, 150.2, 161.2.

(4-Bromophenyl)(4-methoxyphenyl)sulfane (Table 2, entry 3)^{21b} : Yellow gummy oil; IR (neat) : 2998, 2886, 1486 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.83 (3H, s), 6.92 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.03 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 7.34 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 7.42 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz); ¹³C NMR

(CDCl₃, 125 MHz) : δ 55.4, 115.3 (2C), 119.4, 123.6, 129.5 (2C), 132.0 (2C), 135.7 (2C), 138.3, 160.2.

4-(4-Methoxyphenylthio)benzotrile (Table 2, entry 4)^{21c} : Colourless oil; IR (neat) : 2980, 2889, 2206, 1445 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.86 (3H, s), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 7.07 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 7.44 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 7.47 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz) : δ 55.6, 108.2, 115.7 (2C), 116.3, 119.1, 126.2 (2C), 132.4 (2C), 137.2 (2C), 147.5, 161.1.

1-[4-(4-Methoxyphenylsulfanyl)-phenyl]-ethanone (Table 2, entry 5)^{21d} : Colourless oil; IR (neat) : 2976, 1689, 1448 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.51 (3H, s), 3.82 (3H, s), 6.94 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 7.07 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 7.45 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 7.76 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz) : δ 26.4, 55.4, 115.4 (2C), 121.4, 125.9 (2C), 128.8 (2C), 133.9, 136.8 (2C), 146.9, 160.7, 197.1.

Di-(4-bromophenyl)-sulfane (Table 2, entry 6)^{21b} : White solid; m.p. 111–113 °C; IR (KBr) : 2976, 2898, 1447 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.16–7.18 (4H, m), 7.42–7.46 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz) : δ 121.6 (2C), 132.6 (4C), 132.7 (4C), 134.6 (2C).

2-(2-Bromophenylsulfanyl)pyridine (Table 2, entry 7)^{21e} : Colourless liquid; IR (neat) : 3047, 1573, 1448, 1417 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.91 (1H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz), 7.02 (1H, t, *J* 6.08 Hz), 7.23 (1H, t, *J* 7.45 Hz), 7.32 (1H, t, *J* 7.45 Hz), 7.48 (1H, t, *J* 7.62 Hz), 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 7.62 Hz), 7.68 (1H, d, *J* 7.90 Hz), 8.43 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 120.4, 122.1, 128.3, 129.4 (2C), 130.4, 132.8, 133.8, 136.4, 136.9, 149.8, 159.2.

3-(4-Chlorophenylthio)pyridine (Table 2, entry 8)^{17c} : Yellow oil; IR (neat) : 3070, 3043, 1566, 1473, 1406, 1091, 1014, 819, 704 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.23–7.28 (5H, m), 7.57–7.60 (1H, m), 8.47–8.55 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 122.8, 128.3 (2C), 131.2, 131.4 (2C), 131.9, 132.6, 136.8, 146.6, 149.5.

2-(3,5-Dimethylphenylthio)pyridine (Table 2, entry 9)^{21f} : Colourless oil; IR (neat) : 3041, 2917, 1600, 1573, 1560, 1447, 1416, 1144, 1124, 849, 758, 688 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.33 (6H, s), 6.89 (1H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz), 6.94–6.97 (1H, m), 6.98 (1H, s), 7.22 (2H, s), 7.39–7.45 (1H, m), 8.40–8.42 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 21.1 (2C), 119.6, 121.1, 130.2, 130.9, 132.5 (2C), 136.6, 139.2 (2C), 149.4, 161.9.

2-(4-Chlorophenylsulfanyl)thiophene (Table 3, entry 10)^{17c} : Colourless liquid; IR (neat) : 3057, 1579, 1475, 1438, 1217, 1022, 738, 688 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.11–7.38 (5H, m), 7.50–7.58 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 126.1, 127.2 (3C), 127.6 (2C), 128.0, 131.3, 136.1, 137.1.

1-[5-(Pyridin-2-ylsulfanyl)-thiophen-2-yl]-ethanone (Table 2, entry 11) : White solid, m.p. 68–70 °C; IR (KBr) : 3080, 2987, 1652, 1558, 1415 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.54 (3H, s), 7.04–7.08 (2H, m), 7.30 (1H, t, *J* 4 Hz), 7.51–7.55 (1H, m), 7.64–7.66 (1H, m), 8.43 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 26.9, 121.1, 121.6, 132.7, 136.2, 137.3, 139.0, 148.7, 149.9, 159.4, 190.2; HRMS calcd. for C₁₁H₉NOS₂ [M+H]⁺ 236.0198; found 236.0199.

Conclusion

The present procedure using a basic ionic liquid as phase transfer agent in water provides a very efficient and green methodology for the synthesis of unsymmetrical diaryl sulphides by a simple reaction of aryl/heteroaryl sulphides and aryl/heteroaryl thiols catalysed by CuO nanoparticles. The notable advantages offered by this procedure are operational simplicity, general applicability, compatibility with different functional groups and high isolated yields of products. Both the ionic liquid and CuO nanoparticles can be recycled for several times, which make this procedure most cost effective, sustainable and greener.

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge the financial support from DST, New Delhi for the J. C. Bose Fellowship to BCR (Grant no. SR/S2/JCB-11/2008). DK thanks CSIR, New Delhi for his fellowship.

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